

PRE-INTERVIEW QUESTIONNAIRE TO COLLECT THE DEMOGRAPHICS

Question	Choices Provided
Full name	
What is your current role (job title)?	
How long have you been in the industry (total industry experience)?	
What is your team (team name)?	
What is the team size (number of people)?	
Which types of patches are you working with?	Security patches, Non-security patches, Both, Other (please specify)
What types of software components are you in charge of patching?	Operating System (OS), Applications, Custom Inhouse Software Applications, End of Life (EOL) Software, Other (please specify)
How many machines/devices do you manage?	
What type of machines/devices do you manage?	Client machines (e.g., desktops, laptops, etc.), Servers, Mobile devices (e.g., phones and tablets), Routers/network devices, Embedded devices/Internet of Things, Other (please specify)
What are the operating systems on the machines/devices that you manage?	

INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

Warm-up Questions

Q1. Can you briefly walk me through your responsibilities in the security patch management process?

Current tools/automation support in security patch management

Q2. What tools do you use in security patch management tasks?

- When do you use them (i.e., which task in which phase)?
- How does the tool help in security patch management tasks?
- Does the tool require human involvement at any point to proceed with the task?
- If yes, can you explain why? When does it need human input?

Limitations of current tools/automation support in security patch management

Q3. What challenges do you experience in dealing with these tools?

- Can you give me some examples of such challenges you have experienced?
- Why do you think they are challenging?
- In your experience, what situations are the most challenging to handle and why?
- How do you overcome these challenges? Can you please provide some examples?

Needs for better automation/tool support in security patch management

Q4.1. What are the situations or security patch management tasks that are currently not supported by automation in your process?

- Can you explain why they are manual?

Q4.2. What tasks do you wish would have been better supported by the technology, if any?

- What kind of support do you expect from an improved tool?
- How do you anticipate such kind of a tool will help reduce patching delays?
- Any specific features you think are important to have in such a tool?

Q4.3. Have you heard about artificial intelligence (AI) or machine learning?

- How do you think AI can help bring efficiency in the process?
- In your opinion, do you think it is possible to replace human involvement with AI in the security patch management process?

Q4.4: Any related points that we missed but you would like to reflect on?